

DIGITALIZATION AND INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY OF THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Introduction

The scope of creativity in our country is expanding every year. New houses, large factories, modern infrastructure facilities are being built. Naturally, in order to carry out such large-scale works in a high-quality and timely manner, qualified builders and designers, stable organizations are needed.

There are about 22,000 construction-contracting organizations in our country, and most of them do not keep information on the number of employees and professional qualifications.

The fact that all constructions in the regions have been handed over to single customer service organizations has a negative impact on the indicators. While in advanced foreign practice, construction safety, quality and results are controlled, in our country all efforts and resources are spent on process control, and quality is secondary.

It is necessary to create a healthy competitive environment among the project institutes, develop clear criteria for conducting tenders based on foreign experience, and introduce an electronic system in this regard.

Improving the norms and rules of urban planning and the activities of single customer service organizations has become a requirement of today.

The level of use of information technologies in the construction sector remains low. In particular, the processes of creating projects, carrying out expertise, issuing construction permits, and controlling construction-contract works are still being done on paper. A geoinformation system that provides information on where and what can be built for investors and entrepreneurs has not been established.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 13, 2020 No. PF-5963 "On additional measures to deepen reforms in the construction sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan", a strategy for modernization, rapid and innovative development of the construction sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025 was developed.

The purpose of the strategy is to implement centralized changes in the construction industry, aimed at forming modern methods of managing the construction industry, increasing investment attractiveness in the implementation of projects, and introducing innovative solutions to the construction industry.

According to the strategy developed on the basis of the decree, the main directions of modernization, rapid and innovative development of the construction industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan were defined as follows:

- digitalization of the construction industry by creating additional subsystems and databases;
- modernization of the regulatory framework in the field of urban development and adaptation of foreign regulatory documents;

- improvement of the system of complex development of settlements;
- to improve the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the indicator "Obtaining construction permits" in the "Doing Business" international index by simplifying some permit procedures in the construction sector;
- development of the mortgage loan market and the construction of multi-apartment houses by attracting public funds for the construction of housing on the basis of a share in the construction of housing real estate;
- application of innovative technologies to development of building materials and construction of objects;
- step-by-step transition to enlarged indicators in mutual calculations between participants of investment projects;
- improving the principles of licensing, taking into account the liberalization of the institutional framework, strengthening the potential of project and contract works;
- improvement of the system of expert work by canceling the state expertise in the estimate part of the project;
- improvement of the construction quality control system by directing the state, authorship and technical control to the non-state sector;
- organization of modern project institutes with the participation of advanced foreign companies by selling a package of shares to advanced foreign investors;
- improvement of the system of training, retraining and improvement of qualifications of personnel in the field of construction, taking into account the use of modern and innovative methods of training;
- formation and strengthening of the institution of non-state customers, taking into account the liberalization of the state segments, when implementing projects from state and equivalent sources of financing;
- development of scientific potential in the field of construction and architecture by increasing the effectiveness of fundamental, research and applied scientific researches and developments;
- to strengthen the requirements for labor protection and safety equipment during construction and installation works at construction sites;
- development of human capital, improvement of material and technical support of construction bodies and institutions, creation of new mechanisms of social and material stimulation of workers.

It is proposed to implement the following target indicators for the implementation of the 2020-2025 strategy of modernization, rapid and innovative development of the construction industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- By 2025, the operation of the electronic platforms of the national information system "Transparent Construction" will be covered up to 100% throughout the republic;
- Increase the share of Eurocode adaptation in the field of urban planning to 50% by 2025, taking into account the geological, natural-climatic, seismological and other characteristics of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- By 2025, the share of information on the objects of the state urban planning cadastre geographic information system, taking into account the expansion of geoportal functions, will be published for open use;

- Improving the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the direction of "Dealing with Construction Permits" of the international index "Doing Business Index" from the current 61.7 points to 78.2 points by 2025;

- establishment of 15 modern project-research institutes by 2025 with the involvement of advanced foreign project organizations;

- By 2025, increase the share of non-governmental organizations performing customer functions to at least 25 percent of the total number of objects included in the Investment Program;

- By 2025, the share of the introduction of the "volumetric method" should be increased to 25% of the total number of construction objects in the republic..

The strategy defines the goals, tasks and priority areas of the development of the construction industry, the directions of transformation and reform of the construction industry in 2020-2025, the development of proposals and scientific ideas based on the experience of the transformation of the construction sector of foreign countries and taking into account world trends in the field of construction.

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